

Computing topic/content associations: putting a taxonomy, phrase index, and SQL to work

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Abstract

A method for computing associations between nodes in a topic taxonomy and content items in a corpus of tech books is described. Taxonomic context is taken into account in order to increase the probability that links respect node-specific semantics when dealing with terms that have different meanings in different contexts. In addition, a method for rapidly computing term co-occurrence is given.

Keywords:

content linking, evidence cluster, phrase index, polysemy, SQL, term co-occurrence, topic taxonomy

In memory of Louise Heinink (25/8/1969 – 17/12/2011)

1. Introduction

At Packt we've recently embarked on the construction of a taxonomy of technology topics, starting with data science. Analysis of a handful of our core data science titles has yielded an initial taxonomy of around 800 topics. The first application is a topic explorer, currently in live beta (<https://www.packtpub.com/topic>), that allows users to navigate the conceptual space of data science and from the topic nodes access relevant content at various levels of granularity.

When building the topic explorer, one of the issues to be addressed was how to establish links between taxonomy nodes and relevant content, e.g. book chapters or chapter sections. Previously I've reported on the construction of phrase indexes and their use for discerning related pairs of items within content corpora [1], and on the application of phrase indexes in full-text search using SQL [2]. Now I discuss the combination of a topic taxonomy with interrogation of a content phrase index using SQL to help define high-relevance associations between taxonomy topics and content items.

Semantic intelligence

To define a set of associations between topics and content items one can do far worse than simply search the content phrase index for each topic term, one-by-one, in accordance with the method outlined in ref. 2. Indeed, in essence that is the initial approach we have taken when building the beta version of the Packt topic explorer. We find, however, that for some topics the results leave

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something to be desired, especially when the data science taxonomy topics are linked to the whole Packt library. For example, the links for ‘clustering’, as it pertains to the data science sense of the term, also include links to content about server clustering with Kubernetes, for instance. The method lacks semantic nous, in other words, and this necessitates a certain amount of manual link curation. The thought we are now pursuing is that the taxonomy itself could supply the intelligence needed to automatically filter out poor links for topic terms that have several distinct meanings in different sub-fields of tech.

2. Method

The methodology we’ve been investigating employs a single, albeit rather complex, SQL query which effectively consists of two parts, with the taxonomy figuring in both. The first part interrogates the phrase index for the taxonomy topic of interest, e.g. ‘machine learning’, to give us a set of content items mentioning the topic. Also included in this part of the query are any equivalent terms (synonyms) for the topic term, e.g. ‘ML’ is defined in our data science taxonomy as an equivalent term for machine learning.

Evidence clusters

The second part of the query filters the set of content items (book chapters) matching a taxonomy topic term and/or its synonyms so as to retain just those content items whose parent books are sufficiently rich in what we refer to as *evidence terms*. These are additional terms that provide – surprise! – evidence that a piece of content is about the subject to which the topic term relates, in the sense indicated by the term’s occurrence at a particular location of the taxonomy and not in some other sense.

For each taxonomy term we want to link to content, we derive from the taxonomy a cluster of evidence terms. The terms making up this cluster are the taxonomic relatives of the topic term we’re focusing on, such as its sibling nodes, child nodes, and ancestor nodes. For granular topics buried deep in the taxonomic hierarchy, there may be half a dozen ancestor nodes, or even more, while higher-level, broader topics will have few ancestors. Since we store our taxonomy as a set of SQL tables, we can extract the evidence cluster terms for any particular taxonomy topic readily enough with straightforward queries. We can then programmatically construct the second part of our link-building query around the extracted evidence cluster.

A composite topic/content association query

What does this look like in practice, when expressed in SQL form? I suggest you brace yourself at this point, for the composite query is not a thing of beauty. Here’s an example, in which we look for content about Android Virtual Devices (AVDs), assuming (for illustrative purposes) that the relevant evidence terms are ‘android’, ‘android studio’, ‘java’, and ‘mobile development’ (**QUERY1**):

```
SELECT packt_content_id, AVG(taxtermsig) AS avttsig FROM (SELECT
content_items.packt_content_id, (CAST(term_links.term_count AS FLOAT) /
(terms.corpus_count/terms.host_count)) AS taxtermsig FROM content_items,
term_links, terms WHERE term_links.packt_term_id = terms.packt_term_id AND
content_items.packt_idx_fid = term_links.packt_content_fid AND term IN
('android virtual device', 'android virtual devices', 'avd', 'avds') AND
isbn IN (SELECT isbn FROM (select isbn, SUM(term_sig) AS sigsum,
AVG(term_sig) AS sigav FROM (SELECT isbn, (CAST(term_links.term_count AS
FLOAT) / (terms.corpus_count/terms.host_count)) term_sig FROM
content_items, term_links, terms WHERE term_links.packt_term_id =
terms.packt_term_id AND content_items.packt_idx_fid =
```

```

term_links.packt_content_fid AND term = 'android' UNION SELECT isbn,
(CAST(term_links.term_count AS FLOAT) /
(terms.corpus_count/terms.host_count)) term_sig FROM content_items,
term_links, terms WHERE term_links.pactk_term_id = terms.pactk_term_id AND
content_items.pactk_idx_fid = term_links.pactk_content_fid AND term =
'android studio' UNION SELECT isbn, (CAST(term_links.term_count AS
FLOAT) / (terms.corpus_count/terms.host_count)) term_sig FROM
content_items, term_links, terms WHERE term_links.pactk_term_id =
terms.pactk_term_id AND content_items.pactk_idx_fid =
term_links.pactk_content_fid AND term = 'java' UNION SELECT isbn,
(CAST(term_links.term_count AS FLOAT) /
(terms.corpus_count/terms.host_count)) term_sig FROM content_items,
term_links, terms WHERE term_links.pactk_term_id = terms.pactk_term_id AND
content_items.pactk_idx_fid = term_links.pactk_content_fid AND term =
'mobile development' ) AS foo GROUP BY isbn) AS bar WHERE sigav > 1.5 AND
sigsum > 4.0)) AS blah GROUP BY packt_content_id ORDER BY avttsig DESC;

```

More beast than beauty, then, but with suitable reformatting the inner structure of the query becomes apparent:

```

SELECT packt_content_id, AVG(taxtermsig) AS avttsig FROM (
SELECT content_items.pactk_content_id, (CAST(term_links.term_count AS
FLOAT) / (terms.corpus_count/terms.host_count)) AS taxtermsig FROM
content_items, term_links, terms WHERE term_links.pactk_term_id =
terms.pactk_term_id AND content_items.pactk_idx_fid =
term_links.pactk_content_fid AND term IN ('android virtual device',
'android virtual devices', 'avd', 'avds')
AND isbn IN (SELECT isbn FROM (
    SELECT isbn, SUM(term_sig) AS sigsum, AVG(term_sig) AS sigav FROM (
        SELECT isbn, (CAST(term_links.term_count AS FLOAT) /
        (terms.corpus_count/terms.host_count)) term_sig FROM
        content_items, term_links, terms WHERE
        term_links.pactk_term_id = terms.pactk_term_id AND
        content_items.pactk_idx_fid = term_links.pactk_content_fid
        AND term = 'android'
        UNION
        SELECT isbn, (CAST(term_links.term_count AS FLOAT) /
        (terms.corpus_count/terms.host_count)) term_sig FROM
        content_items, term_links, terms WHERE
        term_links.pactk_term_id = terms.pactk_term_id AND
        content_items.pactk_idx_fid = term_links.pactk_content_fid
        AND term = 'android studio'
        UNION
        SELECT isbn, (CAST(term_links.term_count AS FLOAT) /
        (terms.corpus_count/terms.host_count)) term_sig FROM
        content_items, term_links, terms WHERE
        term_links.pactk_term_id = terms.pactk_term_id AND
        content_items.pactk_idx_fid = term_links.pactk_content_fid
        AND term = 'java'
        UNION
        SELECT isbn, (CAST(term_links.term_count AS FLOAT) /
        (terms.corpus_count/terms.host_count)) term_sig FROM
        content_items, term_links, terms WHERE
        term_links.pactk_term_id = terms.pactk_term_id AND
        content_items.pactk_idx_fid = term_links.pactk_content_fid
        AND term = 'mobile development'
        ) AS foo GROUP BY isbn)
    AS bar WHERE sigav > 1.5 AND sigsum > 4.0) )
AS blah GROUP BY packt_content_id ORDER BY avttsig DESC;

```

Worth quickly mentioning is that the phrase index, stored in PostgreSQL, consists of three main tables: *content_items*, which stores information about, yes, the content items making up the

books corpus; *terms*, which contains the indexed phrases and their corpus statistics (columns *corpus_count* and *host_count*); and *term_links*, which associates phrases with content items and stores (in column *term_count*) the number of times a phrase occurs in a content item. (See ref. 2 for further details.)

The basic SELECTION of content items matching our notional taxonomy term (Android Virtual Device) and/or its synonym (AVD) is highlighted above in bold. (Note that terms are lowercased during indexing, and the query reflects this.) Then comes the filter to retain only content items (book chapters) from ISBNs that match certain conditions. In the above example, the filter contains four SELECT groups, one for each evidence cluster term, and these are combined using the UNION operator to pick out the ISBNs that match any of the evidence cluster terms. For each ISBN we compute the sum of the significance values (sigsum) for all the cluster terms and the average significance value across all the cluster terms (sigav), and the penultimate line of the query picks just those ISBNs that exceed particular threshold values. (By significance we mean the ratio of the frequency of a term in a content item to the term's average frequency across the corpus.) Finally we wrap the query with another SELECT that aggregates multiple results for the same content item.

When we run the query in the query command shell against a phrase index of 185 books in the mobile development category, the results look like this:

packt_content_id	avttsig
9781787125360_02	4.25
9781783986101_02	2.7416666666666667
9781788473699_01	2.4777777777777774
9781786467959_06	2.1
9781785887420_08	2.0666666666666667
9781849698863_01	1.8888888888888886
9781786467447_04	1.4666666666666668
9781785887420_09	1.4
9781800563438_01	1.3
9781787282537_02	1.25

...

In the first column are the IDs of the book chapters in the corpus that match our query, i.e. which mention the term 'android virtual device', or its equivalent term 'avd', in the context of a book that is rich in our evidence cluster terms. The values in the second column are the average significance values, as defined above, for the taxonomy term and its synonyms in relation to the listed chapters. The results comprise just the chapters that survive the evidence filter, i.e. which mention the evidence cluster terms at a level above the significance threshold defined in terms of the sum and average aggregate functions.

If we look at the top four results in more detail, it can be seen that they are of gratifyingly high relevance:

9781787125360_02 (4.25) – *Android System Programming, [Chapter 2.] Setting Up the Development Environment* – contains the section 'Installing Android SDK and setting up an Android Virtual Device'

9781783986101_02 (2.74) – *Android Application Development with Maven, Chapter 2. Starting the Development Phase* – contains the section 'Creating an AVD'

9781788473699_01 (2.48) – *Android Development with Kotlin, Chapter 1. Starting with Android* – contains the section 'Setting up Android emulators'

9781786467959_06 (2.1) – *Android Studio 2 Essentials - Second Edition, Chapter 6. Tools* – contains the section 'The AVD Manager'

Cluster terms applied to clustering

In addition to the phrase index of mobile development titles, we've also created a phrase index of 715 recent and popular books spanning all nine categories of tech that make up the Packt library (data, programming, web development, mobile, game development, cloud and networking, security, IoT and hardware, and business and others). This provides the opportunity to test the methodology against the problem case of 'clustering' mentioned above. Suppose we are interested in linking the taxonomy node for the data science sense of the term 'clustering' to relevant content. Now if we run just the first part of the query in isolation we obtain a list of content items that mention clustering (**QUERY2**):

```
SELECT content_items.packt_content_id, (CAST(term_links.term_count AS
FLOAT) / (terms.corpus_count/terms.host_count)) AS taxtermsig FROM
content_items, term_links, terms WHERE term_links.packt_term_id =
terms.packt_term_id AND content_items.packt_idx_fid =
term_links.packt_content_fid AND term IN ('clustering') order by
taxtermsig DESC;
```

packt_content_id	taxtermsig
9781787284395_11	9.76923076923077
9781801819312_10	8.692307692307692
9781789956399_1	8.384615384615385
9781789955248_14	8.307692307692308
9781789955750_11	8.076923076923077
9781789956399_2	7.846153846153846
9781801078313_12	7.153846153846154 <-- (A)
9781789959413_4	6.923076923076923
...	
9781789954043_3	1.9230769230769231
9781838823412_10	1.9230769230769231
9781803237480_8	1.9230769230769231 <-- (B)
9781788990547_6	1.7692307692307692
...	

The results set consists of some 261 rows, and while most of the listed chapters are relevant to the data science sense of clustering, some are not. Especially egregious, for example, is the seventh result (9781801078313_12), indicated by (A) above, which is a chapter from the book *Mastering Windows Server 2019* entitled 'Redundancy in Windows Server 2019'. Why does this chapter rank highly in the results? Inspection of the chapter ToC (table of contents) provides the answer:

```
Network Load Balancing (NLB)
Configuring a load-balanced website
Failover clustering
Clustering tiers
Setting up a failover cluster
Clustering improvements in Windows Server 2019
Storage Replica (SR)
Storage Spaces Direct (S2D)
Summary
Questions
```

The chapter contains numerous mentions of the term 'clustering' – over 90 – but these mentions clearly relate to a very different sense of clustering to the sense in which it is used in data science. Further down the results list, in 41st place, we encounter another such result, 9781803237480_8

(indicated by (B) above), which is a chapter from *Continuous Delivery with Docker and Jenkins* entitled 'Clustering with Kubernetes'.

Seeking now to take into account the context of 'clustering' in our draft data science taxonomy, we can derive from the taxonomy an evidence cluster that includes the ancestor terms *unsupervised learning*, *machine learning*, and *data science*, and child terms *hierarchical clustering*, *k-means clustering*, and *silhouette score*. If we build out the second part of our earlier topic/content association query around those six terms, then when we run the full query (QUERY1) we obtain 61 results, the top 20 being these:

packt_content_id	avttsig
9781787284395_11	9.76923076923077
9781801819312_10	8.692307692307692
9781789956399_1	8.384615384615385
9781789955750_11	8.076923076923077
9781789956399_2	7.846153846153846
9781789959413_4	6.923076923076923
9781800200708_2	6.153846153846154
9781801811910_8	6.076923076923077
9781800200708_3	5
9781789952292_2	4.923076923076923
9781789952292_3	4.538461538461538
9781800568877_10	4.384615384615385
9781788295864_9	3.6923076923076925
9781800560307_10	3.5384615384615383
9781789959413_3	3.3076923076923075
9781800563452_13	3
9781800200708_1	2.923076923076923
9781789952292_1	2.076923076923077
9781788990547_7	2
9781788990547_6	1.7692307692307692

Note that 9781801078313_12, from the Windows Server title, has dropped out of the list, and so has 9781803237480_8, from the Docker/Jenkins title. The remaining results represent book chapters where clustering is mentioned, within books where the evidence cluster terms occur at levels above the defined thresholds.

3. Discussion

The results obtained so far are highly promising, although further experimentation with a variety of taxonomy terms is needed to confirm that the approach generalizes well. In addition, it would seem prudent to compare a variety of rules and methods for composing the evidence clusters. Do larger clusters, created by, for example, expanding the context of a taxonomy node to include parental siblings and their children (i.e. the node's cousins), perform better – result in subjectively better topic/content associations – than more narrowly drawn clusters? Clusters could be made larger still by having them include a taxonomy node's co-occurring terms – those terms which tend to occur frequently in content that contains the taxonomy node term.

Co-occurring terms

Having a SQL phrase index is a great aid to the derivation of co-occurring terms, for we can run queries like this (QUERY3):

```
SELECT distinct(term) FROM
(SELECT term, packt_content_id, ((term_links.term_count *
terms.term_word_count) / (terms.corpus_count/terms.host_count)) AS
term_sig FROM content_items, term_links, terms WHERE
```

```

term_links.packt_term_id = terms.packt_term_id AND
content_items.packt_idx_fid = term_links.packt_content_fid AND
term_links.term_count > 8) as foo
WHERE foo.term_sig > 10.0 AND packt_content_id IN
(SELECT packt_content_id FROM content_items, term_links, terms WHERE
term_links.packt_term_id = terms.packt_term_id AND
content_items.packt_idx_fid = term_links.packt_content_fid AND term IN
('convolutional neural network', 'cnn', 'convolutional neural networks',
'cnns') AND term_links.term_count / (terms.corpus_count/terms.host_count)
> 1.5)
ORDER BY term;

```

This example returns the terms that co-occur with ‘convolutional neural network’, by looking for terms that are relatively frequently occurring (*term_count* > 8) and of high significance (*term_sig* > 10.0 when multiplied by the number of words in a phrase, so as to boost longer phrases), in the content items (book chapters) in which ‘convolutional neural network’ (etc.) occur. When run against the 715-title cross-category index the following phrases are returned:

term	

#xd7	fully connected layers
-1	function to generate
-4	generate
3 #xd7	generate a batch
analytics platform	generating
artificial neural	generator
artificial neural networks	generator network
attention	image
autonomous	input image
autonomous driving	input matrix
batch	knife analytics
batch size	knife analytics platform
books github repository	learning
cats and dogs	looks as follows
chapter 9	maximum value
cifar-10 dataset	network
code snippet	neural network
computer vision	neural networks
computer vision and pattern	number of epochs
conference on computer vision	object detection
convolution layer	operation
convolution operation	preceding
convolutional layer	preceding code
convolutional neural networks	preceding code results
data distribution	preceding code snippet
deep	real
deep learning	real data
define the function	recognition
discriminator model	relu activation
discriminator network	running the code
distribution	samples
documentation at https	size
driving	size of 3
face	stride of 1
face detection	stride of 2
face recognition	time-series data
facial recognition	train the model
fake	training phase
fake data	training process
fashion-mnist dataset	two-dimensional
filter	variable called
fully connected layer	vision and pattern recognition
	words
	(85 rows)

This list of raw phrases from the phrase index contains a fair number of what appear on the face of it to be ‘junk’ terms. By filtering the list against the taxonomy, retaining only those phrases that are taxonomy terms (plausible instances of which are shown above in bold), one obtains the taxonomy terms that co-occur with the specified taxonomy term (in this case ‘convolutional neural network’). One needs to guard against the possibility of conflating different senses of a term, however, by which I mean inadvertently deriving and pooling the co-occurrences of different senses of a term.

Query bootstrapping

One way of avoiding sense conflation would be to manually create lists of titles relevant to each taxonomy term T having sense $S(T)$, and regard only terms from *those* titles as co-occurring terms for T . Automation is always attractive, however, and it might be enabled by exploiting, in something of a bootstrapping process, the composite topic/content association query presented earlier (QUERY1). The methodology would be to use that query to first identify content items in the corpus that employed the taxonomy term of interest (let’s call it $T[\text{int}]$) in the particular sense $S(T[\text{int}])$ implied by its taxonomic context, based on an evidence cluster comprising just the taxonomic relatives of $T[\text{int}]$. The content items identified in this first step would then be used to compute, in a second step, the co-occurring terms of $T[\text{int}]$ (using QUERY3). Because an evidence cluster of taxonomic relatives has already been used to constrain the content items from which the co-occurring terms are computed, we can have some confidence that the co-occurring terms identified will in the main be those associated with sense $S(T[\text{int}])$ rather than a different sense, one aligned with some other context. The co-occurring terms thereby derived could then be associated with $T[\text{int}]$ and added to that node’s evidence cluster, permitting the computation of a new set of content links for $T[\text{int}]$ on the basis of an evidence cluster now expanded by its co-occurring terms.

Contextual scope

After that rather chewy digression on the possible expansion of evidence clusters by the addition of co-occurring terms, I want to turn now to contextual scope. The method for computing relevant content links for taxonomy topics given here, as embodied in QUERY1, was framed in terms of the identification of taxonomically relevant book chapters, and evidence that mentions of a topic term within a chapter were taxonomically relevant was sought at the level of the parent book. One likely effect of this will be to overlook significant mentions of a topic term that occurs in taxonomically relevant chapters, when those chapters occur in books whose other chapters deal with other, possibly unrelated, subjects, i.e. do not contain the evidence terms that are sought by the composite query. This may be a virtue, for example when one wishes to direct users towards chapters that focus on a particular taxonomy topic only where they occur in books that relate *as a whole* to the broader topical context of the taxonomy topic term.

Sometimes we will not wish to be restrictive in this way: we might wish to show users *all* chapters relevant to a taxonomy topic, even if those chapters are surrounded by unrelated material. In this case the use of evidence clusters as described thus far will likely prove a hindrance. However, what QUERY3 reminds us is that we can constrain queries by narrower content identifiers than ISBN, e.g. by book chapter identifier. Thus we could modify QUERY1 to return book chapters that mention the taxonomy topic term of interest, when those chapters themselves contain the evidence cluster terms at above-threshold levels. The context of those matching chapters would be immaterial.

Refinements and variations

Many other variations of the ideas articulated here can be conceived. Different ways of scoring and ranking results could be tried, for example. Should some taxonomic relatives be weighted more heavily than others when considering the evidence for relevance provided by evidence cluster terms? Also, mention should be made of the fact that the length of content items is not taken account of in the queries presented here. The reasons for this are twofold. First, it was felt that because the book chapters in the Packt corpus are generally quite similar in length, it would not affect the results too much to overlook chapter length differences. Secondly, by ignoring content length differences we ensure that query expressions are no longer than necessary, aiding the exposition of the underlying ideas. Nonetheless, it would be possible to refine the term significance calculations by making use of the *word_count* column that exists within the *content_items* table. The degree of statistical over- or under-representation, or significance as I dub it, of a term T in a content item is given by the ratio of its frequency in the content item to its frequency in the corpus, and those frequencies are properly expressed as the number of occurrences of T divided by the content length in words. A simple query can be used to derive overall corpus word count.^{3,4}

4. Concluding remarks

The work which has been described shows that SQL, although at half a century old not exactly the latest kid on the technology block, can be a powerful medium through which to represent term data in books content and in a taxonomy. When it brings them together, their capabilities are multiplied. It also testifies to the flexible utility of a content phrase index, which likewise represents decades-old thinking. (The phrase indexing work reported in ref. 1 and drawn on here began in the late 1990s, to be picked up again two decades later.) As we enter the uncharted technological waters of AI, and in particular what at the current time some are predicting to be the choppy waters of AI that is unconstrained by effective or psychologically plausible models of the world against which to check its emanations, it is perhaps in some sense reassuring that the 'bag of words' conceptual framework continues to demonstrate value. Of that framework, it looks, to adopt a canine metaphor, as though it's a case not of *farewell, faithful hound* so much as *there's life in the old dog yet*.

References

1. Powell, A. (2020) Phrase indexing and the identification of related academic research content. *Cambridge Open Engage*: <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2020-7zd6k-v2>.
2. Powell, A. (2022) The hybrid SQL approach to full-text search. *Zenodo*: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6256261>.

³ SELECT SUM(content_items.word_count) FROM content_items;

⁴ The 715-title phrase index yields a corpus word count of 61,975,916 words, which equates to a plausible-sounding 86,680 words per title.